

Using real-world data to study the efficiency and effectiveness of care for patients with diabetes: CONCEPT-DIABETES study PROTOCOL

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ABSTRACT

CONCEPT-DIABETES is part of CONCEPT, a coordinated research initiative of five projects that aims at analyzing chronic care effectiveness and efficiency of care pathways in diabetes, congestive health failure, breast cancer and stroke. This project arose under the umbrella of REDISSEC (Research Network on Health Services and Chronicity) and continue functioning under RICAPPS (Research Network on Chronicity, Primary Care and Health Promotion). As common denominator, CONCEPT assumes the relevance of care pathways as independent factors of health outcomes using data from real life world (RWD) from eight Spanish Regional Health Systems.

In the specific case of CONCEPT-DIABETES, the focus is on assessing the effectiveness of a set of clinical practice actions and quality improvement strategies at different levels (patient-level,

health-care provider level and health system level) on the process and health outcomes of patients with type 2 diabetes (T2D) using process mining methodology. It is a population-based retrospective observational study, centered on all T2D patients diagnosed in five Regional Health Services within the Spanish National Health Service, that will assess to what extent clinical practice guidelines (CPG) are being implemented in real life and which are their effects, including information from all the patients' contacts with the health services using the electronic medical record systems of Primary Care data, Specialist Care data, Hospitalizations, Urgent Care data, Pharmacy Claims, and also other registers such as the mortality and the population register. As part of CONCEPT, the methodological approach includes: a) the analysis of the pathways of the patients; b) cost analyses and efficiency of pathways and interventions; c) methodology development to integrate pathways to construct prediction models and d) methodology development to create decentralized infrastructure built on RWD.

To achieve this aims, we will apply process discovery to identify and characterize the longitudinal trajectories experienced by patients with T2D across the healthcare system and will compare, by conformance checking, those trajectories with theoretical trajectories derived from CPGs in terms of process indicators and pharmacological treatment recommendations. Second, we will estimate the impact of these trajectories on diabetes related complications using traditional and new analytical process mining methods. Finally, we will evaluate the effectiveness and economic impact of the implemented strategies in diabetes control in relation to process and outcome indicators.

Keywords: protocol; health services research, health care pathways, population-based cohort, type 2 diabetes, process mining, clinical practice guidelines, comparative effectiveness, common data model, CONCEPT-DM2.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is one of the most prevalent chronic diseases, affecting 537 million adults worldwide.¹ In addition to its high prevalence, patients with type 2 diabetes (T2D) have an increased risk of micro- and macrovascular complications, which can be profoundly disabling and life-threatening.² In Spain, the prevalence of DM2 is 10.3% in the range of 20-79 years, bearing an associated annual cost per patient of \$3,005.8.¹ Healthcare providers, commissioners and policymakers must meet the increasingly complex needs of these patients, despite limited resources.

To enhance health outcomes for individuals with diabetes, various multidisciplinary expert committees periodically release and adapt clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) including recommendations on all components of diabetes care.³⁻⁵ In the Spanish context, the last update of the strategy for diabetes in the National Health System of Spain was published in 2012.⁶ The Spanish Primary Care Diabetes group (redGDPS) updated its guideline on T2D in 2018,⁷ and publishes algorithms of prevention and treatment of the disease annually. Despite particular regional adaptations, all guidelines agree on the main components of diabetes care and specify recommendations that include periodic metabolic controls and assessments of cardiovascular (CVD) risk factors and complications. However, the extent to which these recommendations permeate routine clinical practice and are being effective and cost-effective remains uncertain. Globally, some recent studies have shown that health professionals' adherence to the American Diabetes Association (ADA) guidelines in some critical aspects of the care process, such as the glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) measurement frequency or pharmacological treatment modifications, is extremely low.⁸ Other studies have gone further, and have shown a protective effect of adhering to guidelines on diabetes complications, reducing the risk of stroke, kidney failure and death,⁹ as well as hospitalizations.¹⁰ At national level, although significant improvements have been observed in various indicators of the care process in some regions,¹¹ it seems that compliance with follow-up recommendations in these patients is still low,¹² exhibiting disparities among health professionals and regions.¹³ The evaluation of the effect of compliance with national guidelines on the course of diabetes in our context is very scarce, and deserve more attention.

A central focus of these guidelines is achieving adequate glycemic control, given its direct relation with micro- and macrovascular complications.^{14,15} Suboptimal control can primarily be attributed to two factors: patient non-adherence to prescribed treatments and clinical or therapeutic inertia among healthcare providers, defined as reluctance to initiate or intensify

therapy according to evidence-based clinical guidelines.^{16,17} Consequently, current clinical guidelines recommend to change glucose-lowering medication if HbA1c goals are not achieved after three months. However, patient adherence and therapeutic inertia and their effects on T2D remains largely underexplored in clinical practice.

In addition to the publication of CPGs, national and regional governments design specific quality improvement strategies to increase effectiveness in diabetes care. Many of these strategies focus on introducing changes at the health system level with special attention to providing continuity in treatment at all levels of care.¹⁸ Other interventions target professionals, primarily through audits and providing feedback on clinical performance,^{18,19} and others target patients, primarily providing empowerment training and self-care tools.¹⁸⁻²⁰ Based on evidence, many of these strategies significantly improve metabolic control and CVD risk factors.¹⁸ In this direction, and at a regional level, the Government of Navarre approved the Navarre Strategy of Integrated Care for Patients with chronic diseases and multimorbidity.²¹ Within this framework, different actions were implemented throughout 2019 on the structure and coordination of the Regional Health Service, such as the creation of the Diabetes Section in the University Hospital of Navarre,²² the creation of an electronic medical record system shared by all levels of care, the creation of a system of stratification of patients according to their complexity and the creation of an electronic monitoring system, which provides information to the health care provider on global information (dashboards) and at the patient level (control panels). Similarly, the Government of Aragón approved the Integrated Care Strategy for Diabetes Mellitus, which was updated in 2021,²³ and incorporates an electronic monitoring system that provides information to the health care provider on process and outcome indicators in these patients.

To analyze the care provided by the health system to patients with DM2, to identify and characterize the care pathways that these patients follow and to assess whether the interventions implemented are effective and efficient are complex tasks, because they require the analysis of the complete experience of patients in all contacts with health care providers. The increasing availability of patient-level digital data, together with the increment on computing and analysis capabilities, provide an opportunity for the development of research focused on analyzing the impact of continuity of care (i.e., integrated care) on outcomes in chronic patients, in particular adding the process mining approach to the study of the effectiveness and efficiency of care.²⁴ For the particular case of T2D, recent studies show the possibility of using administrative health databases for research purposes in our context²⁵ and the possibility of applying process mining to describe the trajectories of patients with chronic diseases, such as T2D.²⁶ These trajectories could help answer questions such as how patients

with T2D move through the system, how close they are to their theoretical trajectory derived from evidence-based CPGs, what are the consequences of following different trajectories or what are the underlying causes of following different trajectories.

Regarding the economic analysis of T2D (ie, cost calculation, budget impact studies or complete economic evaluations), the existing evidence is partial, as the complete care trajectory or the complete spectrum of patients treated in a healthcare system has not been considered. Additionally, it frequently refers to institutional contexts other than the Health System of Navarre – Osasunbidea (SNS-O), and in any case, it is not based on the information provided by RWD generated by patients with diabetes.

The CONCEPT-DIABETES project aims to analyze the effectiveness and efficiency of a number of actions in metabolic and CVD control and in the reduction of chronic or acute complications in five population-based cohorts of patients with DM2 built on RWD of the following Spanish regional health services of Navarre, Aragon, Basque Country, Valencia and Canary Islands. To do this, first the trajectories experienced by patients with DM2 throughout the health system in the five regional contexts will be described, and how much these differ from the theoretical trajectories that represent the care recommendations according to the diabetes guidelines will be identified. The impact that these trajectories have on health outcomes will be evaluated. These pathways will be analyzed using process mining, which will provide trajectories that represent patients' actual exposures to care services and interventions over time, and which will be considered key predictors of health outcomes. All these actions and their effects will be compared between the cohorts, which will allow us to carry out a comparative effectiveness study between the different regional health services.

HYPOTHESES

- Patients with T2D experience different care trajectories depending on their demographic and clinical characteristics, and some of these trajectories deviate significantly from the theoretical trajectories proposed by clinical guidelines.
- The evolution of the disease in patients with DM2 depends not only on their sociodemographic and clinical characteristics, but also on the adherence of their health personnel to the CPGs, both in indicators process and in therapeutic recommendations.
- There are differences in the management of diabetes in the different Regional Health Services, which in turn are related to differences in health outcomes.

- Process mining provides useful information for a rapid and reliable understanding of the trajectories that patients follow through the health system, while allowing the assessment of the impact of the proximity between the pragmatic and theoretical care trajectory on health outcomes.

OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this project is to assess the effectiveness of a set of processes and strategies in the management of T2D in the National Health System using the process mining methodology, and compare these results with those derived from more standardized statistical methods, in terms of model quality, predictive capacity and information provided.

Specific objectives:

1. To identify and characterize both the healthcare trajectories and the therapeutic trajectories experienced by patients with T2D across the healthcare system.
2. To compare both the healthcare trajectories and the therapeutic trajectories experienced by patients with T2D with theoretical trajectories derived from CGPs in terms of process indicators and pharmacological treatment recommendations.
3. To assess the effect of healthcare provider adherence to CGPs on health outcomes and clinical costs.
4. To compare the degree of compliance with medical care standards, prescription patterns and clinical outcomes between regional health services, taking into account the different frequencies of the trajectories obtained for each cohort.
5. To compare traditional and new analytical methods based on process mining in terms of modeling quality, predictive capacity of the derived models and information provided (instrumental methodological objective).

METHODS AND ANALYSIS

Study design and subjects

This is an observational longitudinal retrospective study based on five population-based cohorts of patients with T2D from different regional health systems of the SNS: the Navarrese Health Service - Osasunbidea (SNS-O), the Basque Health Service - Osakidetza (Osakidetza), the

Aragonese Health Service (SAS), the Valencian Health Service (SVS) and the Canarian Health Service (SCS).

The cohort will be open and will include all patients who, on January 1, 2017 to December 31, 2022, had active health card and code T90 of the international classification of primary care version 2 (CIAP-2) or code 250 of the international classification of diseases (ICD-9CM) in the records of: ATENEA (Navarre), Osabide-PC (Basque Country), PC-SAS (Aragon), PC-SVS (Valencia), and PC-SCS (Canary Islands), after excluding patients with no contact with the health system from 2017-01-01 to 2022-12-31. The follow-up period will extend from January 1, 2017 to December 31, 2022. See details of inclusion and exclusion criteria in CONCEPT-DM2 data model, which is freely available at Zenodo in the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/7778291>.²⁷ All analyses that require a baseline data, such as those based on trajectories, will be conducted in incident cases, which is the sub-cohort of patients who had active health card and code of Type 2 Diabetes from January 1, 2017 to December 31, 2022.

The study will be conducted on the entire universe of data, from which the different trajectories will be inferred. It is estimated that the resulting cohort will consist of approximately 50,000 patients with DM2 from Navarre, 100,000 from the Autonomous Community of Aragón, 170,000 from the Canary Islands, 180,000 from the Basque Country and 200,000 from the Valencian Autonomous Community. Given the population nature of the study, we do not perform sample size calculations, but the available number of cases will provide high precision in the estimation of differences between trajectories and in the estimation of outcomes.

Sources of information

Information will be obtained from different clinical-administrative databases. A Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA, or EIPD in Spanish) will be conducted with the help of the data protection Officer (DPO, or DPD in Spanish). All technical departments involved in data extraction will agree the extraction procedure to guarantee high standards for data security. In the case of Navarre, the main data will be obtained from BARDENA (Results Analysis Base of Navarre), which is a population data warehouse of the Navarre Health Department that integrates individual-level information generated at any level of health of approximately 97% of the Navarre population, totaling more than 660.000 people (see data resource profile on Gorricho et al, 2023).²⁸ Complementary, the mortality registry will provide information on the date and cause of death (main and secondary), and the census/registry will provide socioeconomic characteristics, at the individual and aggregate level.

Similarly, information from Osakidetza, SAS, SVS and the SCS will be obtained following the specific procedures of each region. For those regions that have not a population data warehouse like BARDENA, core data will be obtained from the Primary Care (PC) Electronic Health records. This will be complemented with 1) the CMBD database (Minimum Basic Data Set), which will provide information on hospital discharges in relation to CVD events, potentially avoidable hospitalizations and hypoglycemia, 2) with the databases for prescriptions and dispensations of outpatient pharmacological treatment both from primary care and specialized care (SC) and 3) with the electronic health records of SC to provide information on the consultations. Utilization rate of the health electronic systems of these regions is 100% since 2008-2010. In general terms, they present high quality in the validity of the coding. For instance, the sensitivity and specificity for the T2D code in the case of Navarre health records in 2005 were 96% and 99%.²⁹ In relation to the control, diagnostic and lifestyle parameters, we will consider valid data for baseline those recorded in the last 15 previous months, except for some variables such as CIAP diagnoses, for which the last available value will be considered independently from the moment of inclusion (see detailed information in the DataModel).²⁷

Outcome measures and other variables

The whole list of variables considered are given in the aforementioned DataModel²⁷ and represented graphically in the data model diagram given in Figure 1.

A: Process indicators (with baseline and follow-up dates). To have (or not) biannual measurement of HbA1c; to have (or not) annual measurements of total cholesterol, blood pressure, weight and smoking status and to have received annually influenza vaccine. For the screening for complications, we will use to have (or not) annual diabetic foot examination, an ocular exam (conducted by PC and by ophthalmologist) every three years, and to have annual albuminuria and glomerular filtration rate measurements. Indicators were selected in agreement with Variation in Medical Practice Atlas – Atlas VPM, with very few exceptions because of availability.³⁰

B: Intermediate endpoints (with baseline and follow-up dates): The main intermediate endpoint will be having controlled HbA1c (<7/8/8.5% depending on patient characteristics). Intermediate outcomes of clinical parameters will be HbA1c (%), Systolic and Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg), LDL (mg/dL), HDL (mg/dL), Triglycerides (mg/dL), weight, BMI (Kg/m²), waist circumference (cm), albumin-creatinine ratio, serum creatinine, glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) and smoking.

C: Pharmacological treatment (with baseline and follow-up dates): Prescriptions with date, formulation, dose and quantity, drugs dispensed in the follow-up and drug codes will be used

for the following therapeutic groups according to the International Anatomical and Therapeutic Classification (ATC): oral antidiabetics (A10B), insulins (A10A), antiplatelet agents (B01AC), beta blockers (C07), ACEI/ARB (C09) and statins (C10AA).³¹ Theoretical therapeutic pathways for each predominant clinical condition will be those derived using the redGDPS algorithm for the T2D treatment (see Figure 1).⁷

D: Final endpoints (prevalence of complications and events): The main endpoints will be: a) change of predominant clinical condition b) hospitalizations (any cause) and c) cardiovascular event (defined as in Tamayo et al 2023).³²

E: Other variables at baseline (for adjustment). Regarding Individual socio-demographic and lifestyle, we will include sex, age, status (active/pensioner), country of birth, pharmaceutical co-payment category, educational level, smoking (not smoker, ex-smoker<1 year, ex-smoker>1 year, having stopped smoking, smoker), alcohol (not drinker, moderate drinker, regular drinker), physical activity (incapacity, inactive, partially active and active). Socioeconomic variables of the area (basic health zone): average income of the census track. Regarding clinical variables, we will include duration of diabetes at baseline, CVD disease, chronic kidney disease, comorbidities (Charlson index), atrial fibrillation, retinopathy and hypoglycemia.

Data analysis and process mining

Once the global cohort is defined, we will create the event log, which requires the transformation of the dataset into an event data structure, where each event refers to a case, and activity and a point in time. The quality of the data will be evaluated in terms of date agreement and missingness of data. For data analysis, the different phases of process mining will be used:

1. Process Discovery: Identification and characterization of both healthcare trajectories and therapeutic trajectories (Objective 1) will be conducted using process discovery, which will allow to model patient exposure to the healthcare system through trajectories using the bupaR package in R, pm4py package in Python and modeled as a graph. A procedure for clustering the therapeutic traces, such as the hierarchical clustering algorithm, will be used to summarize the processes. This will group traces with similar sequential behavior, measuring this similarity with Levenshtein distance, which will allow to identify and characterize the different therapeutic processes.
2. Conformance checking: The inferred trajectories will be compared with the theoretical trajectories, which will be derived from CPGs (see Figure 2) and manually coded as a Petri Net graph (Objective 2). This will be conducted using conformance checking methodology

available in the pm4py package of Python. Graph dissimilarity measures, such as ‘fitness’, will be used to quantify how close each pathway is from the theoretical one. Fitness values ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 indicating the highest similarity. This conformance checking analysis will be used to assign each patients a fitness value, and also to compare the similarity between the trajectories of the different regions and the theoretical one among regions (Objective 4).

3. Prediction modeling: The impact of the trajectories on the health outcomes of these patients (hospitalizations, CVD events and complications) will be assessed through time dependent cox models and joint latent class models, including each health outcome as dependent variable, the patients trace’s fitness at different time intervals as main covariate and other important demographic and clinical variables, such as age, sex and charlson as covariates (Objective 3).
4. Methodological comparison: To quantify to what extend the process mining methodology provide a more real global picture compared with the classical methodology, we will also analyze the effect of GPC adherence on health outcomes using two time-windows, one to capture fulfilment of process indicators and the other one to fit a Cox regression model to capture the main events.
5. Economic evaluation: The economic analysis will be linked to the conformance checking analyzes and the effectiveness analyses. A basic cost analysis will be performed to determine the differences between the costs of received and theoretical healthcare, and between the trajectories of the participating regions (Objective 3). The economic analysis will be developed by the SCS group (in one subproject).

Limitations

This project has several limitations. First, it uses data from clinical practice, which implies uneven quality and degree of completion of some of the variables. However, the high number of patients with diabetes, the information from five regional health services and the fact that a large number of professionals are involved in data entry greatly minimize the risk of bias. Second, there are some key variables, such as capillary hemoglobin tests, or hypoglycemia, which could determine a change in the treatment regimen, and are under-recorded. Third, it focuses on patients with diagnosed T2D, so people with undiagnosed T2D and those exclusively using private health institutions are not included, which may lead to information bias, although we expect the proportion of patients in these groups to be small. And finally, the fact that this pathology is chronic and highly prevalent causes a diversity of possible trajectories to emerge

for each of the profiles and moments of patient follow-up, which forces to focus on incident cases, to homogenize the start of the follow-up.

DISCUSSION

CONCEPT-DIABETES aims to provide solid responses to some of the global strategies of the Health, Demographic Change and Well-being challenge of the Spanish Strategy for Science and Technology and Innovation.³³ First, we will use the RWD framework to generate a cohort that will recreate the real experience of the care received for all the patients with diabetes of the National Health Systems in five Spanish Autonomous Communities of Spain. Second, we will try to depict the way in which health care is provided in terms of adequacy, effectiveness and efficiency using statistical and novel methodologies, taking into account that the results of the project will be transferred not only to scientists, but also to clinicians and decision makers. Likewise, in terms of increasing translational capacity, CONCEPT-DIABETES is designed to add value not only to the science and innovation system, but also to the public health system. With regard to science and innovation system, the methodologies explored and applied, in particular process mining techniques, are pioneering both in the field of health services and policy research and in that of clinical sciences. On the other hand, the implementation of a decentralized federated infrastructure that aims to cover different research questions on the same cohort using RWD is totally new in both research fields. Furthermore, the open access delivery of CONCEPT outputs, from data models to reports with results, including this protocol, will allow any other researcher in the system to robustly replicate our methods in their cohort of patients from other contexts.

CONCEPT-DIABETES will also respond to relevant questions presented in international, national and regional CPGs for diabetes management. More specifically, it will describe and evaluate the actual care provided to patients with T2D in terms of adherence to CPGs and how these factors influence the evolution of the disease in different Regional Health Services from different parts of Spain, such as Navarre, Aragon, the Basque Country, Valencia and the Canary Islands. Thus, the project responds to several of the recommendations advocated by the Diabetes Strategy of the National Health System (2012 update) both in the line of Research, Training and Innovation, as 1) it promotes the use of Primary Care clinical data for clinical research and evaluation, 2) it is a longitudinal, cooperative and multicenter epidemiological study that assess the role of risk factors of diabetes and its complications and, 3) it includes the perspective of evaluation of social inequalities, since it incorporates variables such as educational level as predictors in care

trajectories. In summary, this project is designed to provide scientifically valid, reliable and useful information for decision making as part of the continuous improvement on the path towards healthcare excellence.

ETHICS AND DISSEMINATION

The study, observational in design and using non-identifiable and non-traceable retrospective data, will be carried out in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, the International Guidelines on retrospective observational studies, the European GDPR Regulations (General Data Protection Regulation) already mentioned, to the Spanish Laws on ethical considerations, and to the regional ones, such as Resolution 1387/2017 of the Navarrese Health Service-Osasunbidea. Only people who usually work with information systems will have access to the source information, which will be anonymized before it is made available to researchers. The study protocol was favorably evaluated by the Ethics Committee of Clinical Research of Navarre (Project 97/2019, August 28, 2019).

The results will be disseminated in at least two manuscript that will be submitted to peer-reviewed and high-impact healthcare and/or methodological journals. The data model of this project is already available since it has been published in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/7778291>).²⁷ Other project intermediate deliverables such as the data analysis plan and data monitoring plan will be published in open science repositories such as Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). Moreover, this project will also has online presence through social networking pages such as Twitter to disseminate the findings to the wider public. Our findings will be presented at national and international healthcare conferences focused on the quality and effectiveness of diabetes management and the application of process mining in healthcare.

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FIGURES

Figure 1. CONCEPT-DM2 Data model diagram.

Figure 2. RedGDPS 2023 DM2 treatment algorithm⁷

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